

CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IN THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY**Bibutova Shakhlo Sadullayevna***independent researcher of the Tashkent State University of Economics***КОРПОРАТИВНОЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ В ХИМИЧЕСКОЙ ОТРАСЛИ С УЧЁТОМ РАЗВИТИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ****Бибутова Шахло Саъдуллаевна***независимый соискатель Ташкентского государственного экономического университета***Abstract**

The article examines the issue of corporate governance in the chemical industry, taking into account the development of the digital economy. As you know, the chemical industry is considered one of the important and highly profitable sectors of the economy, and, therefore, all the possibilities of digital corporate governance solutions in this industry have a special place in the economy. In addition, attracting investors and developing digitalization in the chemical industry helps improve the corporate governance system, which indicates the relevance of this topic.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается вопрос о корпоративном управлении в химической отрасли с учётом развития цифровой экономики. Как известно, химическая отрасль считается одним из важных и высоко прибыльных сфер экономики, и, следовательно, все возможности цифровых решений корпоративного управления в данную отрасль имеет особое место в экономике. К тому же привлечение инвесторов и развитие цифровизации в химической отрасли способствует совершенствованию системы корпоративного управления, что является и говорит об актуальности данной тематики.

Keywords: digitalization, chemical industry, corporate governance, sustainable development, competitiveness.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, химическая отрасль, корпоративное управление, устойчивое развитие, конкурентоспособность.

Introduction.

It is important to note that the development of the chemical industry plays an important role in improving the living conditions of people around the world. In 2021, the volume of chemical production in Uzbekistan increased by 6.1% due to the application of modern management approaches at chemical industry enterprises. Developed countries showed growth of 3.1%, and developing countries - by 7.2%.

Currently, improving the enterprise management system in the chemical industry and increasing competitiveness have become pressing issues. In the conditions of modern market relations, the active development of industrial sectors, the production of competitive products and the organization of a flexible management system capable of adapting to a changing environment are important. It is necessary to create corporate forms of management, change management methods and leadership styles, as well as introduce digitalization into the management system. It is important to use a management model that allows you to develop management decisions in a timely, fast and efficient manner in modern industrial structures. The new development strategy of Uzbekistan for the period from 2022 to 2026 highlights priorities including the development of the chemical industry, as well as increasing the volume of chemical production to 2 billion US dollars by increasing the level of natural gas processing from 8% to 20%. To effectively implement these priority tasks,

it is necessary to improve enterprise management systems.

Theoretical aspects of the research.

Corporate governance in the chemical industry, taking into account the development of the digital economy, has several theoretical aspects that are worth considering.

Digital transformation: The development of the digital economy provides the chemical industry with new opportunities to improve production processes, optimize management and increase efficiency. Digital transformation includes the adoption of new technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), data analytics and process automation.

Innovation Management: The evolving digital economy requires companies in the chemical industry to proactively manage innovation. Corporate governance should help create a culture of innovation and encourage and support research and development of new products, processes and business models.

Risk management: In the digital economy, new types of risks arise related to cybersecurity, data protection and privacy. Corporate governance must pay particular attention to managing these risks and implementing appropriate safeguards.

Data management: The digital economy provides companies in the chemical industry with vast amounts of data. Corporate governance must include effective data management, collection, storage, analysis and use

for making management decisions and optimizing business processes.

Supply Chain Management: In the digital economy, there is integration and digitalization of supply chains. Corporate governance should pay attention to optimizing and automating procurement, logistics and inventory management processes using digital technologies.

Cybersecurity. With increasing dependence on digital technologies and interconnected systems, cybersecurity is becoming a critical aspect of corporate governance. Chemical companies need to implement strong cybersecurity measures to protect their sensitive data, intellectual property and operational infrastructure from cyber threats. This includes creating secure networks, implementing encryption protocols, conducting regular vulnerability assessments, and training employees on cybersecurity best practices.

Compliance and Regulatory Requirements. The digital economy brings new regulatory challenges and compliance requirements to the chemical industry. Corporate governance must place particular emphasis on understanding and complying with relevant laws, regulations and industry standards relating to data privacy, intellectual property rights, environmental protection and product safety. Compliance systems must be integrated into the corporate governance framework to ensure ethical and responsible behavior in the digital environment.

Talent management and professional development. The digital transformation of the chemical industry requires a skilled workforce capable of leveraging technological advances. Corporate governance must include talent management strategies that attract, develop and retain employees with digital competencies. This may include upskilling existing employees, developing a culture of continuous learning, and partnering with educational institutions or technology providers to address skills gaps.

Stakeholder involvement and transparency. In the digital age, stakeholders including customers, investors, regulators and communities have increased expectations of transparency and engagement. Corporate governance must include open communication, stakeholder dialogue and transparent reporting practices.

The use of digital communication channels and technology can facilitate effective stakeholder engagement and enhance trust in the chemical industry.

Ethical considerations. The digital economy raises ethical questions and challenges that need to be addressed within corporate governance. Chemical companies must develop ethical principles and codes of conduct governing the use of digital technologies, data analytics and artificial intelligence. Ethical considerations may include data privacy, algorithmic bias, responsible deployment of artificial intelligence, and the ethical implications of new technologies.

Cooperation and partnership. The digital economy encourages collaboration and partnerships between industry players, technology providers and research institutions. Corporate governance should promote a culture of collaboration and explore opportunities for strategic alliances, joint ventures and knowledge sharing. Collaborative initiatives can spur innovation, accelerate digital transformation, and more effectively address industry-wide challenges.

By incorporating these aspects into their corporate governance practices, chemical companies can navigate the complexities of the digital economy, unlock new opportunities and achieve sustainable growth while maintaining ethical standards and meeting stakeholder expectations.

Analysis and result.

To invest or not to invest in digitalization for the sake of growth and efficiency is now a rhetorical question for chemical industry players. Digital technologies have become an integral part of the value chain. As the global industry recovers from the impact of the pandemic, chemical industry players have increased investments in digitalizing their operations. As of 2022, digital transformation is the second most important capital issue for chemicals companies worldwide, according to the survey. Recent uncertainty caused by the pandemic and geopolitical issues has led to supply chain constraints and material and labor cost inflation, which is holding back chemical industry growth and profitability. They have also prompted chemical industry players to accelerate the digitalization of all functions, with more than 40% of chemical industry companies reporting the disruptive or disruptive impact of digitalization over the past three years.

Table 1

Status of digital projects in the chemical industries¹

Volume	2020	2022
0-25%	6	4
25-50%	16	10
50-75%	41	34
More than 75%	37	52

The chemical industry contributes nearly \$6 trillion to global gross domestic product and supports an estimated 120 million jobs worldwide. No one knows exactly how many chemicals are used in industrial and consumer products, but the number is likely in the hundreds of thousands. These diverse substances include

polymers and plastics, adhesives and coatings, specialty electronic materials, and flavors and fragrances. This pace of digitalization is expected to continue as more than 65% of chemical industry participants expect digitalization to impact their business in more disruptive or disruptive ways.

¹<https://cefic.org/app/uploads/2021/12/Economic-Analysis-of-the-Impacts-of-the-Chemicals-Strategy-for-Sustainability-Phase-1.pdf>

The impact of digitalization on operational competitiveness in the next three years²

	Name	Percent
1.	Supply Chain Planning	68
2.	Sales and order management	67
3.	Purchase	67
4.	Customer service	65
5.	Production and quality management	65
6.	Logistics and distribution	65
7.	Sustainability Area 3	55
8.	Sustainability, area 1 and area 2	52

As the need for an online model for both business operations and customer interactions grows, chemical industry players have witnessed maximum progress in digitalization of administrative functions and customer interactions since 2020. Additionally, with technologies such as automated chemical synthesis and digital tools, 80% of chemical industry companies are expected to move towards this direction.

With recent geopolitical turmoil and fluctuating fuel prices, supply chain constraints have become a key challenge for the global chemicals industry. Given the volatility, it remains a key application area that benefits enormously from digitalization and that digitalization has greatly impacted their supply chain planning over the past three years, with more than two-thirds of survey respondents believing similar impacts will continue over the next three years. As the need for more sustainable supply chains grows, chemical industry players are seeing value in using digital tools to estimate demand, track raw materials to sources, real-time order tracking, automation in warehouses and ports for sorting and security, and optimizing supply networks.

As companies digitize their operations, the risk of cybercrime against the business becomes an inherent concern. As a result, digital or cybersecurity is one of the topics most widely adopted among chemical industry players, especially in the case of basic and petrochemical companies with their huge manufacturing plants.

A wide range of technologies improve the efficiency of chemical functions, from research and development through the value chain to customer service and support. In this dynamic environment, the preference and potential of any particular technology depends on the immediate needs and priorities of organizations. In 2020, chemical industry players' capabilities were heavily focused on improving and integrating data analytics (42%), while according to the 2022 survey, it was more widespread - falling to 35% for data analytics and increasing to 30 % for digital security (from 26% in 2020). However, despite this decline, improved data analytics (35%) and integration (30%) are among the areas of high potential for chemical industry players, followed by digital security (30%), as chemical industry players face increasing challenges, such as data theft and malware, which can not only compromise sensitive data but also stop operations.

At the dawn of Industry 4.0, cost reduction was

perceived as one of the key benefits of digitalization. However, chemical industry players have moved away from this and have benefited from digitalization not only through cost reduction, but also through electronic networks (53%) and customer centricity (51%) - a trait needed to develop a sustainable business in difficult times³.

As chemical industry players explore all the possibilities of digital solutions for their business, new challenges arise. The lack of qualified personnel was a key problem in 2020 for 47% of survey respondents; however, in the current survey, just over a third said it was a problem. Companies currently face challenges in creating a reliable technical infrastructure (40%), meeting investment needs (38%) and developing secure systems (38%).

Conclusion.

Overall, corporate governance in the chemical industry must be adapted to the demands of the digital economy. This includes the adoption of new technologies, risk management, legal compliance, talent development, transparency and ethical standards. Businesses that successfully integrate digital solutions and innovation into their operations can reap significant benefits and achieve sustainable growth in today's chemical industry.

References

1. Алетдинова А.С., Бабкин А.В. и др. Цифровая трансформация экономики и промышленности: проблемы и перспективы. / монография /Под ред. д-ра экон. наук, проф. А.В. Бабкина. - СПб: Изд-во Политехн. Ун-та, 2017. – 807 с.
2. Бакин А.В. Промышленная политика в цифровой экономике: проблемы и перспективы. / труды научно-практической конференции с международным участием., 2017. – 699 с.
3. Бакин А.В. Тенденции развития экономики и промышленности в условиях цифровой экономики. / Коллективная монография. - СПб: Изд-во Политехн. Ун-та, 2017. – 658 с.
4. Alp Ustundag, Emre Cevikcan Industry 4.0: Managing The Digital Transformation, January 2018, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-57870-5, ISBN: 978-3-319-57869-9.
5. Morteza Ghobakhloo, Mohammad Iranmanesh Digital transformation success under Industry 4.0: a strategic guideline for manufacturing SMEs,

²https://revvitysignals.com/sites/default/files/2022/12/PerkinElmer_TheNextFrontier_ebook_final.pdf

³ https://www.ey.com/en_gl/advanced-manufacturing/why-the-chemical-industry-is-prioritizing-digitalization

April 2021, Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print), DOI: 10.1108/JMTM-11-2020-0455.

Internet sites

https://revvitysignals.com/sites/default/files/2022/12/PerkinElmer_TheNextFrontier_ebook_final.pdf

<https://www.ulprospector.com/knowledge/14401/pe-digital-transformation-in-the-chemical-industry-part-1/>

<https://assets.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/images/2015/01/China-chemical-industry-sustainability-201209.pdf>

<https://cefic.org/app/uploads/2021/12/Economic-Analysis-of-the-Impacts-of-the-Chemicals-Strategy-for-Sustainability-Phase-1.pdf>

<https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-management/economic-features-of-chemical-leasing.pdf>

<https://chemical-watch.s3.amazonaws.com/downloads/Chemicals-Management-Software-Guide.pdf>